
ROLE OF THE JUDICIARY IN DEVELOPING THE PRINCIPLE OF EXCESSIVE DELEGATION & ABDICATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses on the evolution of delegated legislation in India, its impact on constitutional values as well as the judiciary's contribution toward shaping and sustaining these ideologies. Although delegated legislation can be vital in its own right, it may lead to problems because of a lack of proper monitoring. This can create a situation of the concentration of power into a few hands, thus threatening the very basis of democratic accountability. Ultra vires or the doctrine of excessive delegation has been regarded as a fundamental foundation for preventing unconstitutional transfer of legislative responsibilities. The study sets forth the standards for excessive delegation and emphasizes that reasonability, respect to the constitution, and absence of arbitrary rule making are essential. It emphasizes how alert and responsive should judiciary be so as to have a fair balanced and accountable governance system.

Keywords: Delegated Legislation, Excessive delegation, Judicial review, Abdication, Essential legislative functions

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This article adopts the doctrinal approach to discuss delegated legislation in India. It seeks to explore its historical origins, constitutional principles, and legal aspects. It uses traditional legal resources like text books, statutes, court cases and journal articles. Legal textbooks act as a basis of knowledge, statutes present a legislative environment, while scholarly articles suggest theories. A qualitative analysis is used in identifying legal principles, doctrines, and interpretations. It is possible to identify patterns, discordances and changes in views through comparative studies of both cases and scholarly opinions. Although this methodology involves interpreting existing legal texts and judicial decisions, these may no longer be in line with the current times. The issue of ethics is crucial and my work complies with the ethical convention on citation and attribution. Therefore, this paper's research methodology brings forth a detailed perception on the delegated law giving significant contributions to the legal discussion amid the limited boundaries.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE:

1. To Understand the constitutional principles governing delegation of legislative authority.
2. To Analyse key judicial pronouncements and tests shaping the doctrine of excessive delegation.
3. To discuss the case of Vivek Sharma vs UOI in the context of excessive delegation.
4. Assessing the judiciary's role in developing and applying principles to prevent unconstitutional transference of legislative responsibilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Delegating legislative and judicial functions to the executive by the legislature has become a common practice in democratic countries. Besides their administrative role, the executive is responsible for promulgating most legislation as a delegate of the legislature, which is referred to as "Delegated legislation." According to Black's Law Dictionary, 'Delegation' is as an act of entrusting a person with the power or empowering him to act on behalf of that person who has given him that power or to act as his agent or representative. 'Delegated legislation' means exercising of legislative power by an agent who is lower in rank to the Legislature, or who is subordinate to the Legislature.²

During the pre-constitution period in India, only conditional legislation was validated by the Privy Council. Hence, delegated legislation was not allowed unless certain conditions were met.³ The Privy Council applied conditional legislation again in the case of *King v. Benori Lal Sharma*.⁴ In this case, the validity of the Emergency Ordinance given by Governor-General of India was challenged. The governor was setting up special criminal courts for a particular kind of offence, but the power to establish any court was given only to the Provincial Government. The judicial committee held that this was not delegated legislation. The Privy Council also held that it was an example of an uncommon legislative power, which allowed the local application of the provisions of the state determined by the local administrative body when it was necessary. However, in the post-constitution period, the Supreme Court of India upheld the delegation of power given to the executive by the legislature in the case of *Raj Narain Singh v. Chairman, Patna Administration Committee Air*.⁵

II. UNDERSTANDING THE PRINCIPLE OF EXCESSIVE DELEGATION AND ABDICATION

The Constitution of India gives the legislature the power to delegate its authority to other authorities and to create policies to implement the laws it enacts. In *D. S. Grewal v. State of Punjab*,⁶ the Supreme Court clarified that Article 312⁷ of the Constitution addresses the

² Meena, D. (2022). An Analysis of the Constitutionality of Delegated Legislation. Indian Journal of Law and Legal Research, 4, 1-11.

³ Queen v. Burah 5 I.A. 178 (1878)

⁴ King v. Benori Lal Sharma [1945] 1 All ER 210

⁵ Raj Narain Singh v. Chairman, Patna Administration Committee Air. AIR 1954 SC 569

⁶ DS Grewal v. State Of Punjab, 1959 AIR 512

⁷ 312. All India Services (1) Notwithstanding anything in Chapter VI of Part VI or Part XI, if the Council of

powers of delegated legislation.

The doctrine of excessive delegation, also known as the doctrine of ultra vires, states that if the legislature delegates its legislative responsibility to another entity in an excessive manner, that delegation is unconstitutional. This theory serves two purposes: first, it ensures democratic accountability in the laws that govern the people; and second, it provides the courts with a clear standard to determine whether a rule or regulation violates the parent statute.⁸

It is a fundamental principle that the legislative function is the primary responsibility of the legislature, and it cannot be delegated to the executive. The determination of legislative policy and its formulation as a rule of conduct are essential legislative functions that must be carried out by the legislature itself. Once the legislature has exercised these essential legislative powers, the ancillary and incidental functions can be delegated to the executive.

It is a widely accepted fact that Parliament does not possess legislative power as an inherent and original power but as power delegated to it by the Constitution. Therefore, Parliament is constitutionally obliged to exercise its legislative functions and cannot legally delegate them to the executive. In Great Britain, excessive delegation of parliamentary powers is a political concern, while in the US and India, it is primarily a judicial concern.

Abdication means abandonment. When the legislature fails to legislate and entrusts the primary function to the executive or any outside agency, there is an abdication of legislative power. Abdication may be partial or total. The legislature can delegate legislative power, but it must not abdicate or efface itself by setting up a parallel legislature. Delegation of

States has declared by resolution supported by not less than two-thirds of the members present and voting that it is necessary or

expedient in the national interest so to do, Parliament may by law provide for the creation of one or more all India services (including an all India judicial service) common to the Union and the States, and, subject to the other provisions of this Chapter, regulate the recruitment, and the conditions of service of persons appointed, to any such service

(1) The services known at the commencement of this Constitution as the Indian Administrative Service and the Indian Police Service shall be deemed to be services created by Parliament under this article

(2) The all India judicial service referred to in clause (1) shall not include any post inferior to that of a district judge as defined in article 236

(3) The law providing for the creation of the all India judicial service aforesaid may contain such provisions for the amendment of Chapter VI of Part VI as may be necessary for giving effect to the provisions of that law and no such law shall be deemed to be an amendment of this Constitution for the purposes of article 368

⁸ Mahak Dua, Doctrine of Excessive Delegation in India - Analysis on RTI (Amendment) Act, 2019 and NJAC Act, 2014, 3 INDIAN J.L. & LEGAL Rsch. 1 (2021).

legislative power does not necessarily amount to abdication or complete effacement. What constitutes abdication and what class of cases are covered by that expression is always a question of fact. A rule of universal application cannot be laid down.

Principles and Criteria for Assessing Excessive Delegation in Legislation

The issue of excessive delegation must be assessed based on three fundamental principles:

1. The essential legislative function of enacting laws and determining legislative policy cannot be delegated.
2. Due to the modern complexities and conditions, it may not be feasible for the legislature to meticulously enact laws for every situation, leading to a need for certain functions to be delegated while maintaining legislative policy guidelines.
3. If the executive is conferred with power in a lawful manner, the delegation should not be considered excessive simply because the legislature could have provided more detailed provisions.⁹

In assessing the legality of a statute's delegation, it is crucial to determine if the delegation involves giving up vital legislative functions and whether the legislature has provided clear policy guidelines for the delegate. If there is an affirmative answer, then it constitutes excessive delegation; however, if the answer is negative, then any challenge would be unsuccessful.

Statutes facing challenges based on excessive delegation should undergo two examinations:

1. Whether they transfer essential legislative functions.
2. Whether the legislature has defined its policies and principles to guide the executive. When determining if a legislating body has exceeded its authority in enunciating policy and principle through legislation, attention should focus on substance rather than mere formalities.¹⁰

III. THE ROLE OF THE JUDICIARY IN DEVELOPING EXCESSIVE DELEGATION PRINCIPLES

A. Judicial Perspectives and Tests (Exploring the English and American Solutions)

⁹ C.K Thakkar, Administrative Law, 2nd Edition, Pg 117

¹⁰ C.K Takwani, Lectures on Administrative law, 5th Edition. Pg 88

In 1950, the Part C States (Laws) Act was enacted, which again provided for the delegation of legislative power. The President of India sought an Advisory Opinion from the Supreme Court on the matter.¹¹ In the context of the discussion about the delegation of legislative powers, the "English solution" and the "American solution" refer to the ways that the legal systems in Great Britain and the United States address the issue of allowing a legislative body to transfer some of its law-making powers to another authority, which is usually an executive body or an administrative agency.¹²

The English Solution and the American Solution are two different approaches to the delegation of legislative power in their respective legal systems. The British legal tradition allows for "conditional legislation" which means that Parliament can delegate certain decision-making or regulatory powers to government ministers or departments. The British courts have generally accepted this practice, so long as the delegation includes clear guidelines and limitations on how the powers can be used. This approach is intended to ensure efficient governance, and the system does not have a rigid separation of powers like in the US. In contrast, the US Constitution establishes a strict separation of powers between the legislative, executive, and judicial branches of government. Historically, the US courts were hesitant to allow Congress to delegate its legislative powers due to this principle of separation of powers. However, over time, the US Supreme Court has established that delegation of certain "nonessential" legislative functions is permissible provided there are adequate standards guiding the use of these delegated powers.

In summary, the English Solution is more flexible and accepting of delegation of legislative power, while the American Solution is more cautious, allowing delegation of certain powers only when they are nonessential and guided by clear standards.

In the Supreme Court, there were varying views on where representation was permitted. While three judges supported the English approach of allowing legislative powers to be delegated, two judges believed that the situation in India resembled that of the US, where representation is limited by the presence of written constitutions.¹³

Judges used two important criteria to determine the extent of permissible delegation: a

¹¹ In re Delhi Laws Act, 1912 A.I.R. 1951 S.C. 332.

¹² Alexandrowicz-Alexander, C. H. "Delegation of Legislative Power in India." *The American Journal of Comparative Law* 3, no. 1 (1954): 72–79. <https://doi.org/10.2307/837126>.

¹³ Ibid

qualitative test and a quantitative test.

1. The quality test for legislative power mandates that it can only be used for subordinate, accessory, or conditional legislation. This implies that the delegated authority can apply to administrative regulations, and determination of facts and circumstances to conform with laws or non-statutory administrative obligations. In summary, only non-essential duties can be delegated.
2. The quantitative test limits the amount of power that can be delivered in a quantitative experiment. The judges held that the legislature should not abdicate sovereignty entirely by delegation, thus preventing abdication. Thus, the representatives must not exceed the quorum to fulfill the role of the legislature in governance.¹⁴

The judges utilized these tests to define the limits of delegation of legislative authority. Whilesome judges supported the English approach, which allows for greater flexibility in the delegation, others favoured the American approach, which imposes tighter restrictions. Ultimately, the judges' viewpoints and the implementation of these tests were instrumental in establishing the parameters and constraints of the delegation of legislative power in India.

B. Judicial Pronouncements on Excessive Delegation: Unpacking Key Cases in India

Prior to the independence, delegated legislation was common in India and was supported by the last court of appeal that is referred here as Privy Council until 1949. To ensure that the Indian legislature remained subservient while meeting the demands of delegation, the Council formulated the formula. The minor importance of the delegated matters were signified in the doctrine of conditional legislation. The privy council in *Queen v. Burah*¹⁵ held that the Indian Parliament has a plenary power to make laws on subjects in relation with its own territory. Maximus *delegatus non protest delegare*¹⁶ applies, but the powers are strictly limited through the Act of British Parliament which established it. The Federal Court however understood that the conditional legislation doctrine has been narrowly construed in *Jatindra Nath Gupta V. Province of Bihar*.¹⁷ Following the independence of

¹⁴ Ibid

¹⁵ Queen v. Burah 5 I.A. 178 (1878)

¹⁶ The legal maxim means that a delegate cannot further delegate his powers

¹⁷ Jatindra Nath Gupta v. Province of Bihar. A.I.R. 1949 F.C 175.

India, the President brought the issue concerning the legality of delegated legislation to the supreme court.

The matter was discussed in the well-known case –*In re Delhi Laws Act, 1912*.¹⁸ Even though seven different lengthy opinions of the court did not establish any well-defined rules, it can be stated that Parliament (together with state legislatures) possesses the right of delegation in order to make the functioning of the Constitution possible. However, there were different opinions of the limit in which such power can be extended, some argued that the Indian legislature had the right to transfer its powers to any extent, so long as it remained within the range where it did not abrogate its functions. Another view held that the legislature should never abdicate these basic law-making functions that involve policy-making and making them into standards. Delegation therefore meant that policy, rules and regulations should be laid down by the legislature.¹⁹

The legitimacy of section 8(2)(b) of the Central Sales Tax Act, 1956 was doubted through excessive delegation in the *Gwalior Rayon Mills v. Assistant Commissioner*²⁰ case. In this section, sales tax can be imposed on interstate sales at either 10 percent or the applicable rate for the sale or purchase of like items within a particular state; whichever one is higher. Appellant states that it is a legislative task to set the tax rate and by failing to set the same the Parliament had breached its legislative functions. SC affirmed the constitutionality of this section but on the extent of delegating power they differed. According to the majority reasoned by Khanna in section 8(2)(b), the clear purpose of this section is to make sure that sales tax central does not erode less than state taxes. This as per Khanna, J., meant that parliament did not transfer its legislative responsibilities. On his part, Mathew, J., concurred, with an even wider understanding of delegation. He took a position that Parliament has wide delegating powers subject only to an implied assumption that it will not relinquish its legislative role to a complete extent. He also suggested that so far as parliament was able to repeal the section, the legislative functions of parliament had not been relinquished.

Mysore Excise Act of 1965, the legality of a specific section 22 was challenged in case of

¹⁸ A.I.R. 1951 S.C. 332.

¹⁹ Joshi, K. C. "Question of Legislative Policy In Delegated Legislation—Recent Cases." *Journal of the Indian Law Institute*, vol. 18, no. 3, 1976, pp. 509–14. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43950444> . Accessed 17 Nov. 2023

²⁰ *Gwalior Rayon Mills v. Assistant Commissioner* A.I.R. 1974 S.C. 1660

*N.K.Papaiah v. Excise Commissioner.*²¹ This section granted the government the authority to determine the rates of excise duty on certain products manufactured in the state. The person challenging the law contended that providing the government with the power to set excise duty rates without clear guidelines was legally questionable. The High Court's ruling was based on the preamble of the Act, which outlined the objectives of raising revenue and discouraging the consumption of liquor. In the SC Justice Mathew expressed uncertainty about whether the Act's preamble provided sufficient guidance for determining excise duty rates. The Supreme Court emphasized that even in the absence of explicit guidelines, it doesn't mean the government has free rein. The legislature can still control delegated powers using different methods. Substituting the doctrine of excessive delegation for legislative control the Supreme Court said that even if there's not a clear guide, the legislature can still control delegated powers through different means, like reviewing rules and having the ability to change or cancel them later. This decision, in a way, adjusted the usual rule that delegation is okay if there's a clear policy or standard.

In the case of *Kerala State Electricity Board*,²² the court upheld the delegation of powers on the basis of a statutory provision or norm contained in the Act. A four-judge majority examined the importance of constitutional order and standards in adjudicating the validity of the delegated statute. They supported that the legislature should establish policies, standards, or guidelines in the representation law. However, it may be noted that A.C. Gupta, J., disagreed, imposing a condition on the representation, finding no statutory provision, norm or guideline in the Kerala Act. On the whole, the Kerala State Electricity Board case emphasized the necessity of a legal system or standard in a delegated legislation. The Court recognized the delegation of power as long as there was a clear provision or standard in the Act.

In the case of *Hamdard Dawakhana v. Union of India*²³ involves the issue of excessive legislative powers. The petitioner challenged the constitutional validity of the Drugs and Magic (Objectionable Advertisement) Act, 1954, on the ground that the power of delegation under Section 3 of the Act is unauthorized and unfettered, and authority has been conferred power to specify diseases and conditions without providing any criteria, standards, or principles for making such specifications. This lack of direction and authority was

²¹ N.K. Papaiah v. Excise Commissioner A.I.R. 1975 S.C. 1007

²² Kerala State Electricity Board v. Indian Aluminium Co. A.I.R. 1976 S.C. 1031

²³ Hamdard Dawakhana v. Union of India, 1960 AIR 554

regarded as an excessive delegation of legislative power beyond the permissible limits of reasonable delegation and consequently, it was held that Part of Section 3 of the Act was inconsistent with the constitution. This case is important because it highlights the importance of ensuring that delegated legislation is properly directed and enforced and that power is prevented from being excessive concentration of power in the hands of the executive²⁴

In the case of *St. Johns Teachers Training Institute v. National Council for Teacher Education*,²⁵ the court provided guidance on deciding whether a particular legislation amounts to excessiveness or not. Several factors must be taken into consideration. These factors include:

- a. the exposition of the law,
- b. grounds of application of the statute, along with its Preamble, the scheme of the law, and
- c. the facts and circumstances that served as a background for the law to be enacted

When a statute is challenged for its constitutionality, it must not be arbitrary in nature and function, and should not violate any provision of the constitution. The principle of reasonableness under Article 14 and Article 19 of the Indian constitution must be followed. Any rule-making function that causes prejudice to a person without the authority or rule of law is invalid by nature and should be declared so.²⁶

In the legal matter of *Ajoy Kumar Banerjee v. Union of India*,²⁷ the court emphasized the necessity for the legislative body to clearly declare their policies and establish definite standards. This responsibility cannot be assigned to any other entity. Similarly, in the case of *D Pandit Banarsi Das Bhanot v. The State of Madhya Pradesh*,²⁸ it was determined that the executive possesses the constitutional power to formulate the regulations of taxation law. Finally, in the case of *D Harishankar Bagla & Anr. v. The State of Madhya Pradesh*,²⁹ the state's executive authority imposed restrictions on exporting cloth beyond state borders, a

²⁴ Jain, M. P. (1960). Constitutional Law—Arts. 19(1) (a), (f) and (g)—Delegation of legislative power—Advertisements—Hamdard Dawakhana v. Union of India. *Journal of the Indian Law Institute*, 2(4), 564-567. <https://doi.org/43949610>

²⁵ *St. Johns Teachers Training Institute v. National Council for Teacher Education* (2003) 3 SCC 321

²⁶ Drishti Meena, An Analysis of the Constitutionality of Delegated Legislation, 4 INDIAN J.L. & LEGALRSch. 1 (2022).

²⁷ *Ajoy Kumar Banerjee v. Union of India*, (1984) 3 SCC 127

²⁸ *Pandit Banarsi Das Bhanot v. The State of Madhya Pradesh*, 1959 SCR 427

²⁹ *Harishankar Bagla & Anr. v. the State of Madhya Pradesh*, AIR 1954 SC 465.

decision which was deemed legally sound by the court.³⁰

The case of *M/S Omkar Agency v. Food Safety & Standards Authority of India*³¹ was a highly debated one, centering around a ruling by the Food Safety Commissioner that sparked controversy. In this ruling, the sale of zarda, pan masala, and gutka was banned under Section 30(a) of the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006. This decision was met with resistance and was eventually challenged in the Patna High Court, where it was ultimately overturned. According to the court's reasoning, since another central law, known as COTPA, explicitly permits the manufacture and production of tobacco and tobacco-based products, a complete prohibition of smokeless products would be unjustifiable. The court also made a strong point that such a ban would constitute an unnecessary delegation of executive power.³²

C. The Case Of Demonetization: Excessive Delegation Or Not?

In the court case of *Vivek Narayan Sharma vs UOI*,³³ Section 26 of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934 was the subject of scrutiny. This section of the RBI Act permits the Indian government to issue an order in the gazette declaring that certain notes issued by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) shall not be accepted as money. This provision can serve as a channel for demonetization of select bank notes.

The petitioners disputed the meaning of "any series" and "any denomination" in Section 26, claiming that they do not include "all series" or "all denominations". The petitioners contended that the RBI Act is guilty of excessive delegation, as it delegates legislative power to the government and RBI in matters concerning delegated legislation. They argued that the RBI Act violates the doctrine of excessive delegation and that the Central Government has been given an unconstitutional amount of power. Section 26 of the RBI Act gives powers to the Central Government to demonetize all notes that are a delegation of legislative power in matters concerning delegated legislation. This provision authorizes both the Bank and the Central Government to propose and execute demonetization. However, this provision empowers the executive branch with considerable legislative authority, which has raised questions about the doctrine of excessive delegation.

³⁰ Mahak Dua, Doctrine of Excessive Delegation in India - Analysis on RTI (Amendment) Act, 2019 and NJAC Act, 2014, 3 INDIAN J.L. & LEGAL Rsch. 1 (2021)

³¹ *M/s Omkar Agency v. Food Safety & Standards Authority of India*, 2016 SCC OnLine Pat 9231

³² *Supra* 24

³³ *Vivek Narayan Sharma vs. UOI* 2017 SCC 1 388

During the case proceedings, the majority of judges held that the government has the right to demonetize any series of all denominations. The court did not agree with the notion of excessive delegation, reasoning that leaving the executive to determine the intricacies involved in the formulation of complex issues, like economic policies, is not impermissible. The court further noted that managing a country's economy requires special skills and a quick adaptation capacity that cannot be guaranteed by the Legislature. Therefore, wide powers of delegating legislation were desirable regarding currency and economics law. However, a minority view held that the words "any series" and "any denomination" in Section 26 have a restricted meaning. The Central Bank cannot recommend that all series of all denominations be demonetized. Instead, the broad action should come from the Central Government through plenary legislation and not just section 26 notification. The dissenting opinion argued that the Centre could not have drawn its powers to demonetize from this Section because the proposal did not originate from the RBI Central Board.

In summary, the case brought to light the ambiguity surrounding Section 26 of the RBI Act and its implications for demonetization. The court's decision that the Central Government has the right to demonetize any series of all denominations has implications for the balance of power between the executive and the legislature. The minority view that the Central Bank cannot recommend demonetization of all series of denominations sheds light on the importance of the role of the RBI Central Board in the decision-making process.

IV. A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXCESSIVE DELEGATION

"Power tends to corrupt, and absolute power corrupts absolutely. Great men are almost always bad men, even when they exercise influence and not authority, still more when you superadd the tendency or the certainty of corruption by authority."- Lord Acton

In the case of *Avinder Singh v. State of Punjab*,³⁴ it was noted that the Constitution has established three distinct branches of government: legislature, executive, and judiciary, all with different powers assigned to them. Discarding any of these powers by any one of the branches will breach or deny the law since it would be against the constitution.

Though excessive delegation in India is a subject which is hard to grasp, the Indian judiciary has built an elaborate procedure for defining the limits of powers that can be delegated. The

³⁴ Avinder Singh v. State of Punjab, AIR 1979 SC 321

judiciary has pointed out through its qualitative and quantitative tests that for delegated legislation to be legitimate, legislative policy, clear standards, and constitutional principles should be adhered to.

Judicial pronouncements demonstrate a changing relationship between the Indian judiciary and parliament. While the Privy Council's conditional legislation doctrine laid the foundation for a flexible approach to delegation, the Supreme Court's opinions in landmark cases like *In re Delhi Laws Act*, *Gwalior Rayon Mills*, and *N.K. Pappiah* have showcased a broad range of perspectives on the extent of permissible delegation.

The courts have continually tried to develop clear principles on this subject, yet there is a continuing debate and criticism in this regard. Nonetheless, the focus on legislated policies or standards exemplified by the *Kerala State Electricity Board* case suggests that such a judicial attitude entails a transparent guideline for delegation. Standardization in all these cases should be made, given that criticisms surround the irregularity in this process which leads to inconsistency in judicial reasoning and the legal results.

Guidance provided in cases like *St. Johns Teachers Training Institute* and *Ajoy Kumar Banerjee* highlights the importance of reasonableness, adherence to constitutional principles, and the avoidance of arbitrary rule-making. This provides a solid foundation for future judicial decision-making and reinforces the need for a principled approach in evaluating the constitutionality of delegated legislation.

While commendable efforts have been made to establish clear tests and guidelines, challenges remain in maintaining consistency, addressing dissenting opinions, and adapting these principles to the ever-evolving socio-legal landscape. The ongoing scrutiny of executive actions demonstrates the judiciary's commitment to upholding constitutional principles and preventing an undue concentration of power. As these principles continue to develop, a vigilant and adaptive judiciary remains crucial for ensuring a balanced and accountable system of governance. The relevance of reasonableness, respect for constitutional ethos as well as the absence of arbitrariness is clearly emphasized by decisions such as *St. Johns Teachers Training Institute* and *Ajoy Kumar Banerjee*. It helps to lay a stable base from which future judicial decision making may be made with some principle in testing constitutionality of delegated legislation. Although attempts have been taken to develop clearly defined tests and standards, issues still persist involving consistency, handling of conflicting views, and ensuring that this principle remains relevant within a

changing socio-legals environment. Close eye and continued scrutiny of the action's executives show the courts' efforts in sustaining constitution principles and avoiding too much power accumulation at one point. The ever-evolving nature of these principles therefore requires a strong and resilient judiciary with an aim of keeping the government in check.

V. CONCLUSION:

In Conclusion, delegation of the legislative authority to the executive must be under the constitutional rules in order to preserve the responsibility and ensure legislation policy. The function of the judiciary in the development and application of the doctrine of excessive delegation is pivotal since it ensures that people's rights are democratically enforceable through legislation, thus establishing a guideline for ruling whether a statute offends the parent law. The principle holds that it is important for such laws to exist only within the context of their corresponding legal framework and such laws should strictly comply with the legislative functions thereof. The doctrine of excessive delegation offers clarity on whether the rule is breaking the parent act of legislation and therefore checking the powers of the executive from going beyond the call of duty in order not to weaken the primary purpose of parliament. Thus, it is important to ensure that delegation of legislative power is confined to legal limits for ensuring democratic accountability as well as legal order.

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